

***Euscyrtus concinnus* (Orthoptera: Gryllidae) – a new rice pest in the Philippines**

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A survey of irrigated rice fields in Batangas province revealed the occurrence of a leaf -and stem-feeding gryllid recently identified as *Euscyrtus concinnus* de Haan (Orthoptera: Gryllidae). This is the first account of the insect as a rice pest in the Philippines.

E. concinnus makes irregular to longitudinal holes in the leaves, leaving the margins almost intact. Intense stem-feeding sometimes causes deadhearts (photo 1). An average of 18- 34 nymphs and adults/m² were found during November. Although both are pestiferous, the nymphs cause more damage than adults and prefer to feed on seedbeds and transplanted rice. The pest does not generally attack the rice plant beyond 75 days after transplanting, but in the absence of alternate hosts or young rice plants, it may feed on the very young rice panicles.

The following grasses and sedges were observed to be alternate hosts: *Echinochloa* spp., *Dactyloctenium aegyptium* (L.) Beauv., *Cyperus rotundus* L., *Digitaria sanguinalis* (L.) Scop., *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn., *Paspalidium flavidum* (Retz.) A. Camus, and *Rottboellia exaltata* L.f.

Photo 1. Damage on the stem (resulting in deadheart) and leaves caused by feeding of *E. concinnus* nymphs and adults.

The adults (photo 2) are 1-1.8 cm in length and pale brown in color, with long antennae and legs that easily detach from the body. The females are longer than the males and can easily be distinguished by their long, spear-shaped ovipositor. This species is also recorded in India, Thailand, and Bangladesh as a pest of rice.

Photo 2 Adult female (left) and male (right) of *E. concinnus*.